

Dithiosulphato-diethylenediamine-cobaltiates.

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Preparation of thiosulphato-cobalt complexes, such as thiosulphato-pentammine-cobaltic salts and thiosulphato-pentacyano-cobaltiates, has already been reported in some previous papers (Rây, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **4**, 64, 325; Rây and Maulik, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1931, **199**, 353). In these, the complex ionic group contained only one thiosulphate radical. It was expected that complexes containing two thiosulphate radicals would result if ammonia could be replaced by a twofold co-ordinating unit or a "chelate" molecule like ethylenediamine in the general method of preparation of thiosulphato-cobalt-ammines (Rây, *loc. cit.*). This has actually been realised and forms the subject matter of the present paper. By a method similar to that employed for the preparation of thiosulphato-pentammine-cobaltic chloride and using ethylenediamine in place of ammonia, a series of dithiosulphato-diethylenediamine-cobaltiates of the general formula $M [Co (S_2O_3)_2 \{C_2H_4 (NH_2)_2\}_2]$ have been prepared: where $M = Na, K, \text{ or } Tl$. In these, the bivalent thiosulphate radical fills up only one co-ordination position as in the previously described thiosulphato-complexes.

A compound of the above composition is likely to exist in two different isomeric forms (*cis* and *trans*), due to a difference in the space distribution of the constituent radicals around the central Co atom, as shown below (En = Ethylene diamine).

Both these isomeric forms have been isolated. The green *trans* salts are more stable under ordinary circumstances, but are transformed into the red *cis* modification in alkaline solutions. The *cis* modification again, as is well known, is capable of resolution into two

optically active enantiomerides. Attempts to resolve the *cis* sodium salt with active strychnine nitrate led to the decomposition of the thiosulphato-complex as the solution of strychnine nitrate reacts acid due to hydrolysis, and the thiosulphato-complexes are very sensitive to acids. The employment of a neutral active body like *d*-triethylenediamine-cobaltic bromide in place of strychnine nitrate did not give any better result. In this case the sparingly soluble triethylenediamine-cobaltic thiosulphate separated out from the solution on evaporation. This indicates that the complex dithiosulphato-diethylenediamine-cobaltic ion undergoes partial hydrolysis as shown below.

This is supported by the conductivity measurement of the sodium salt, for which $\lambda_\alpha = 94$ (approx.), whereas λ_α -value for a uni-univalent sodium salt with a complex anion amounts to about 70 at 25° (Walden, *Das Leitvermögen der Lösungen*, 1924, 11, 189). The value of $\Delta = \lambda_{1024} - \lambda_{32} = 21.4$ also points to the same conclusion.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Sodium Dithiosulphato-diethylenediamine-cobaltiate (trans).

Preparation.—Finely-powdered cobalt acetate (10 g.) was treated with 55 c.c. of 10% ethylenediamine solution; the mixture was shaken till all the salt dissolved. A vigorous current of air was passed through the clear solution for 4–5 hours at a temperature of about 10°. Glacial acetic acid (2 c. c.) was afterwards added to the solution and the latter allowed to stand for some time. 50 G. of $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, dissolved in the least quantity of water, were then added to the mixture, and this was left in a cool place for a day or two. Dark-green crystals, separated by this time, were drained and washed with a little cold water. The crude crystals, thus obtained, were purified by dissolving them in water by prolonged and repeated shaking, filtering off any insoluble residue, and then salting out the pure sodium salt by adding a saturated

solution of NaCl. Twice the volume of the saturated NaCl solution was added and the mixture shaken and allowed to stand for 2 hours. The dark-green shining leaflets separated, were drained washed at first with a little ice-cold water, then twice with 10 % alcohol and finally with absolute alcohol. (Found: N, 13.39, 13.58; S, 30.12, 30.02; Co, 13.98, 13.92; Na, 5.51, 5.47. Na- $[(S_2O_3)_2 \cdot Co \cdot En_2]$ requires N, 13.14; S, 30.04; Co, 13.86; Na, 5.4 per cent).

Properties.—The substance forms sparingly soluble, dark-green shining plates. The solution of the substance is greenish violet in colour, which becomes more violet on dilution. The latter turns red by the addition of alkalis. When warmed with ethylenediamine solution, triethylenediamine-cobaltic thiosulphate is formed. The substance is decomposed by acids with evolution of SO_2 and S. Silver nitrate solution produces a greenish precipitate, which readily turns black.

Equivalent conductivity at 25°.

v ...	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048 litres
λ ...	64.8	63.3	71.9	76.3	80.6	86.2	94 mhos.

As already stated the conductivity values indicate partial hydrolysis of the salt in solution.

As the colour indicates, the substance is evidently a *trans* salt. But in solution, specially on dilution, the green colour gradually becomes more and more violet, showing that an equilibrium between the two modifications exists in solution. The transformation of the *trans* into *cis* variety is effected by the addition of alkalis, and the pure *cis* salt has been obtained, as described below, from an alkaline solution of the *trans* salt.

Isomeric cis Sodium Salt.

Preparation.—A solution of the green (*trans*) sodium salt was treated with a solution of chemically pure caustic soda (0.5 g.) in double-distilled alcohol. The mixture was kept over phosphorus pentoxide in an atmosphere free from CO_2 . When the solution was reduced to a small bulk by evaporation and crystals of the red *cis* salt separated in quantities, the mixture was digested with absolute alcohol, allowed to stand for several hours in an atmosphere free from CO_2 , and the supernatant clear solution was poured off from

the crystals. The washing was repeated till the alcoholic filtrate ceased to react alkaline. The substance was then dried over P_2O_5 . (Found: N, 13.53; S, 30.14; Co, 13.90; Na, 5.45 per cent). The composition is identical with that for the *trans* salt.

Properties.—The red *cis* salt is extremely hygroscopic and highly soluble in water. The solution, when allowed to evaporate in air at the ordinary temperature, deposits green crystals of the *trans* salt. By repeated solution and evaporation it is completely converted into the green *trans* modification.

Potassium Dithiosulphato-diethylenediamine-cobaltiate (trans).

Preparation.—A saturated solution of the *trans* sodium salt was mixed with twice its volume of a saturated solution of KCl. The mixture was vigorously shaken and then allowed to stand for some time. The crystals, separated, were drained, washed at first with ice-cold water, then with dilute alcohol and finally with absolute alcohol. (Found: S, 27.08; Co, 12.34; K, 8.26. $K [(S_2O_3)_2 \cdot Co \cdot En_2]$, $2H_2O$ requires S, 26.8; Co, 12.34; K, 8.16 per cent).

The colour and other properties of the substance resemble those of the *trans* sodium salt. The *trans* salt can be converted into the *cis* variety as described in the case of sodium compound.

Thallium Dithiosulphato-diethylenediamine-cobaltiate (trans).

Preparation.—A solution of thallos nitrate was added, drop by drop, with shaking to a saturated solution of the *trans* sodium salt, when the *trans*-thallium salt was precipitated. Excess of thallos nitrate was avoided. The crystals were drained and washed as described in the previous cases. (Found: Co, 9.37; Tl, 32.68. $Tl [(S_2O_3)_2 \cdot Co \cdot En_2]$, H_2O requires Co, 9.44; Tl, 32.68 per cent).

The substance forms dark-green, sparingly soluble, shining crystals.